

Applying Scrum to Research Software Projects

 Matt Machin ¹

¹ University of Manchester, UK

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Software

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Background Scrum is a modern, agile and widely used software development methodology. Rather than trying to set requirements in stone at the beginning of a project, Scrum embraces the idea that requirements will change during all software projects. It takes an iterative, incremental approach and focuses on regular delivery of working software to customers. Can it be applied to research software projects and if so what are the best approaches?

Focus of the Talk In this talk I will give an introduction to the Scrum methodology covering the main roles, workflow and artifacts. I will then talk about how we have applied Scrum to research software projects in my team over the past 10 years. I will cover: * How to apply Scrum to research software projects * Who should take on which roles within a research project * What has worked well and what not so well * How we have evolved our approach over time

Learning Outcomes / Benefits Attendees will gain a basic understanding of the Scrum methodology and learn how to apply it research software projects.

Target Audience Anyone involved in the development of software in a research focused environment. This could include developers, project managers, team leaders as well as customers / collaborators who want to get software developed.